

Motivators and Barriers of Seasonal Influenza Vaccine Uptake among Adults, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: Understanding the specific barriers for uptaking seasonal influenza vaccine, faced by different demographic groups, can lead to targeted communication strategies that resonate with the community's values and beliefs.

Objectives: To estimate of the rate of uptaking seasonal influenza vaccine in the last season and vaccine acceptance rate in the current season as well as defining motivators for uptaking as well as barriers for not uptaking the vaccine among adult general population.

Subjects and methods: A cross-sectional population-based online survey was conducted among adult population of all nationalities, aged over 18 years and currently living in Riyadh city, Saudi Arabia. An electronic Arabic/English questionnaire was utilized for collecting data. It included four main sections: Socio-demographic, habitual and medical characteristics of the participants, awareness about the importance of seasonal influenza vaccine and source of information about that, attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccine, motivators and barriers of uptaking seasonal influenza vaccine.

Results: A total of 361 participants were included in the study. The age of almost a third of them (36%) ranged between 25 and 34 years whereas that of 9.7% was 65 years and above. Males represented 54.8% of the participants. Overall, 49% of the participants expressed neutral attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccine whereas 34.1% and 16.9% expressed either positive or negative attitude, respectively. The commonly reported motivator to uptake the seasonal influenza vaccine was to prevent illness

More Information

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and reduce influenza complications (78.7%), followed by protection during Umrah and Hajj (37.1%), social responsibility and collective immunity (33.5%) and positive past experience with the vaccine (27.7%) while the most frequently reported barriers of not to uptake the vaccine was fear of side effects (75.9%), followed by misinformation or myths (41%), prior negative experience with the vaccine (29.4%), perceived natural immunity (27.1%) and lack of knowledge or awareness (25.2%).

Conclusion: Majority of adult population in Riyadh expressed either neutral or positive attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccine. The commonly reported motivator to uptake the seasonal influenza vaccine was prevention of illness and reduction of influenza complications while the most frequently reported barrier was fear of side effects.

Introduction

The reluctance or refusal to accept vaccinations despite their availability is termed “vaccine hesitancy” [1]. It is increasingly recognized as a significant obstacle to achieving optimal vaccination rates globally, and this issue has been exacerbated during public health emergencies, such as the COVID-19 pandemic [2]. It can lead to substantial public health challenges, including disease outbreaks and the undermining of herd immunity—both of which can have far-reaching consequences for communities and healthcare systems alike [3].

The interplay of sociocultural factors, misinformation, mistrust in healthcare systems, and individual beliefs significantly shapes attitudes toward vaccines within the community [4]. Furthermore, cultural norms and values can dictate how health information is perceived, leading to varying levels of acceptance or skepticism towards vaccines depending on the individual's background and social influences [5]. For instance, traditions associated with health and wellness may prioritize alternative medicine practices, which can lead to heightened skepticism about Western medical interventions, including vaccinations [6]. Moreover, misinformation—often spread through social media, local networks, and other digital platforms—can create confusion and fear, further complicating the decision-making process regarding vaccinations [7].

Additionally, widespread mistrust in healthcare systems, stemming from historical injustices, perceived inequities in healthcare access, and past negative experiences, can deter individuals from seeking vaccinations [8].

Understanding the specific barriers faced by different demographic groups can lead to targeted communication strategies that resonate with the community's values and beliefs [9].

This study aims at exploring the attitude and defining motivators for uptaking as well as barriers for not uptaking the seasonal influenza vaccine among adult people living in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Subjects and Methods

A cross-sectional population-based online survey was conducted among adult population of all nationalities, aged over 18 years and currently living in Riyadh city, which is the capital and largest city located in the

Central Region of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. It has an approximate population of 7 million, according to 2022 estimated census [10]. Those with no an internet access were excluded from the study.

The minimum required sample size was calculated using the following sample size equation:

$$n = p(1 - p) \left(\frac{Z}{P}\right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Where:

Z is the value from the standard normal distribution reflecting the confidence level that was used ($eZ = 1.96$ for 95%)

E is the desired margin of error (0.05).

P is the proportion of influenza vaccine hesitancy in the population. ($p=0.377$ i.e.37.7% was used) according to a recent Saudi study [11].

Accordingly, the estimated sample size was 361 adults. The non-responses or incomplete response rate were considered as 10%, so the total sample size was increased to ~400 adults.

A convenience non-probability sample was chosen from the eligible population till the required sample size has been achieved.

An electronic Arabic/English questionnaire was utilized for collecting data. It has been adopted from two studies previously conducted in Saudi Arabia [11,12]. Permission to use the questionnaire was requested from the corresponding authors. The questionnaire included four main sections: Socio-demographic, habitual and medical characteristics of the participants: Age, gender, marital status, number of children, nationality, educational level, employment status, monthly income, duration of being a resident of Riyadh, weight in Kg, height in cm, smoking history, working in healthcare, history of chronic diseases, and history of practicing regular exercise; awareness about the importance of seasonal influenza vaccine and source of information about that; attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccine: it was assessed through 14 statements with 5-likert scale; motivators and barriers of uptaking seasonal influenza vaccine were assessed through two questions with multiple responses (Not mutually exclusive). Participants' responses to attitude towards flu vaccination statements were given scores in the way that the higher the score, the more positive

the attitude. Total score was computed and its percentage was estimated and then categorized into three categories based on Bloom’s cut-off points for knowledge, attitude and practice study; ≤59% for negative attitude, 60%–79% for neutral attitude and 80%–100% for positive attitude [13].

Online self-administered questionnaire was distributed using a Google form on different social media tools such as WhatsApp, Twitter and Instagram.

Approval of the local Research and Ethics committee, Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia was obtained prior to data collection (Number of Institutional Review Board “IRB”: E-2460, date: 26/11/2024)

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software program version 28.0 was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics were computed to explore the data. Differences in proportions were compared for significance using Chi Square test and $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 361 participants were included in the study. Their sociodemographic and medical characteristics are presented in Table 1. The age of almost a third of them (36%) ranged between 25 and 34 years whereas that of 9.7% was 65 years and above. Males represented 54.8% of the participants. About two-thirds (66.8%) were married and out of ever married subjects, 83.3% had children. Majority of the participants were Saudi nationals (97.5%). About two-thirds (68.4%) were university degree holders or postgraduates. Nearly half of them (51.8%) were full time employees and 26.3% working in healthcare field. The monthly income of 26.6% of the participants was less than 5000 Saudi Riyals whereas that of 23% exceeded 20,000 Saudi Riyals. Most of them (79.5%) live in Riyadh city for more than 10 years. Most of the participants were either overweight (35.5%) or obese (36.5%). Practicing regular exercise was reported by 38.8% of the participants. Over a quarter of the participants (28.3%) had chronic health problems and 20.2% were current smokers.

Table 1: Sociodemographic and Medical Characteristics of the Participants (n=361)

	Frequency	Percentage
Age (Years)		
18-24	40	11.1
25-34	130	36.0
35-44	64	17.7
45-54	56	15.5
55-64	36	10.0
≥65	35	9.7
Gender		
Male	198	54.8
Female	163	45.2
Marital status		

Single	98	27.1
Married	241	66.8
Divorced	15	4.2
Widowed	7	1.9
Having children *		
No	44	16.7
Yes	219	83.3
Natinality		
Saudi	352	97.5
Non-Saudi	9	2.5
Highest level of education		
No formal education	13	3.6
Primary–	12	3.3
intermediate school	89	24.7
Secondary school	178	49.3
Bachelor's degree	69	19.1
Postgraduate degree		
Employment status		
Unemployed	83	23.0
Employed full-time	187	51.8
Employed part-time	11	3.0
Student	35	9.7
Retired	45	12.5
Working in helthcare		
No	266	73.7
Yes	95	26.3
Monthly income (Saudi Riyals)		
Less than 5,000	96	26.6
5,000 - 10,000	61	16.9
10,001 - 15,000	60	16.6
15,001 - 20,000	61	16.9
More than 20,000	83	23.0
Duration of living in Riyadh city (Years)		
Less than 1 year	24	6.6
1-3 years	13	3.6
4-6 years	15	4.2
7-10 years	22	6.1
More than 10 years	287	79.5
Body mass index		
Underweight	8	2.2
Normal	93	25.8
Overweight	128	35.5
Obese	132	36.5
Practicing regular exercise		
No	221	61.2
Yes	140	38.8
History of chrnic health problems		
No	259	71.7
Yes	102	28.3

Smoking history		
No	262	72.6
Yes	73	20.2
Ex-smoker	26	7.2

Note: *Only for ever-married (n=263)

History of being informed about the importance of the flu vaccine was reported by majority (81.7%) of the participants as displayed in Figure 1. Among them, the most frequently reported source of information was Ministry of Health compaigns (70.5%), followed by healthcare providers other than family physicians (46.1%) and family physicians (43.4%).

Figure 1: History of have Being Informed about the Importance of the Flu Vaccine among the Participants

Figure 2: Source of Information about Flu Vaccine among the Participants (n=295)

Responses of the participants to attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccine statements/questions are summarized in Table 2. Almost two-thirds (65.2%) believed that it is very easy that to access flu vaccination services. Almost half of the participants (51.2%) claimed that they completely controlled getting the flu vaccine. About two-thirds (66.2%) of the participants were either mostly or completely trust the information provided by healthcare providers about the flu vaccine. More than a third of the participants reported never encounter misinformation about the flu

vaccine (37.1%) and not at all concerned about the potential side effects of the flu vaccine (37.7%). About two-thirds of them (67.8%) were likely/very likely to recommend the flu vaccine to others. More than half (57.6%) of the respondents agreed/strongly agreed that it is important for people to get the flu vaccine. About half (53.5%) of the participants reported no pressure at all they feel from their social circles to get the flu vaccine.

Overall, 49% of the participants expressed neutral attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccine whereas

34.1% and 16.9% expressed either positive or negative attitude, respectively.

Table 2: Attitude of the Participants Towards Seasonal Influenza (flu) Vaccine

Statements and questions	Frequency	Percent
The flu vaccine is inconvenient to get		
Strongly disagree	110	30.5
Disagree	88	24.4
Neutral	92	25.5
Agree	48	13.3
Strongly Agree	23	6.4
I am concerned about potential side effects of the flu vaccine		
Strongly disagree	92	25.5
Disagree	77	21.3
Neutral	70	19.4
Agree	86	23.8
Strongly Agree	36	10.0
I do not trust the information provided by healthcare providers about the flu vaccine		
Strongly disagree	150	41.6
Disagree	103	28.5
Neutral	74	20.5
Agree	20	5.5
Strongly Agree	14	3.9
How likely do you think you are to contact the flu this year?		
Very unlikely	7	1.9
Unlikely	31	8.6
Neutral	48	13.3
Likely	192	53.2
Very likely	83	23.0
How serious do you believe contracting the flu would be for your health?		
Not serious at all	65	18.0
Slightly serious	126	34.9
Moderately serious	102	28.3
Very serious	45	12.5
Extremely serious	23	6.4
How much control do you feel you have over getting the flu vaccine?		
No control at all	13	3.6
Slight control	53	14.7
Moderate control	50	13.9
Quite a bit of control	60	16.6
Complete control	185	51.2
How easy or difficult do you find it to access flu vaccination services?		
Very difficult	1	0.3
Somewhat difficult	11	3.0
Neutral	37	10.2
Somewhat easy	77	21.3
Very easy	235	65.2
How positive or negative is your overall attitude toward the flu vaccine?		
Very negative	10	2.8
Somewhat negative	20	5.5
Neutral	98	27.1
Somewhat positive	91	25.2
Very positive	142	39.3
How likely are you to recommend the flu vaccine to others?		
Very unlikely	12	3.3

Unlikely	38	10.5
Neutral	66	18.3
Likely	124	34.3
Very likely	121	33.5
To what extent do you feel that people important to you think you should get the flu vaccine?		
Strongly disagree	9	2.5
Disagree	42	11.6
Neutral	102	28.3
Agree	140	38.8
Strongly Agree	68	18.8
How much pressure do you feel from your social circles to get the flu vaccine?		
No pressure at all	193	53.5
Slight pressure	51	14.1
Moderate pressure	59	16.3
Significant pressure	35	9.7
Extreme pressure	23	6.4
How concerned are you about the potential side effects of the flu vaccine?		
Not concerned at all	136	37.7
Slightly concerned	102	28.3
Moderately concerned	82	22.7
Very concerned	21	5.8
Extremely concerned	20	5.5
How much do you trust the information provided by healthcare providers about the flu vaccine?		
Do not trust at all	13	3.6
Slightly trust	43	11.9
Moderately trust	66	18.3
Mostly trust	79	21.9
Completely trust	160	44.3
How often do you encounter misinformation about the flu vaccine?		
Never	134	37.1
Rarely	81	22.4
Sometimes	90	24.9
Often	37	10.2
Always	19	5.3

Figure 3: Overall Attitude of the Participants Towards Seasonal Influenza Vaccine

Positive attitude was observed among majority of participants aged ≥65 years (86.7%) compared to only 15.6% of those in the age group 35-44 years, p<0.001. Males were more likely than females to express positive attitude (41.4% vs. 25.2%), p=0.003. Married participants were more likely than singles to have positive attitude (39.4% vs. 21.4%), p=0.026. Most of participants with no formal education (76.9%) compared to 27% of those with Bachelor degree expressed positive attitude, p=0.003. Most of retired participants (73.4%) compared to only 20% of students

had positive attitude, p<0.001. Participants with highest monthly income had the highest rare of positive attitude (59%), p<0.001. Overweight and obese participants were more likely than normal BMI participants to have positive attitude (38.3% and 37.9% vs. 23.7%), p=0.011. Participants who reported practicing regular exercise, with chronic health problems and those who being informed about the importance of the flu vaccine were more likely than their counterparts to express positive attitude towards the vaccine, p<0.001.

Table 3: Factors Associated with Attitude of the General Population in Riyadh Towards Seasonal Influenza Vaccine

	Attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccine			p-value*
	Negative N=61 N (%)	Neutral N=177 N (%)	Positive N=123 N (%)	
Age (Years)				
18-24 (n=40)	3 (7.5)	27 (67.5)	10 (25.0)	
25-34 (n=130)	26 (20.0)	71 (54.6)	33 (25.4)	
35-44 (n=64)	14 (21.9)	40 (62.5)	10 (15.6)	
45-54 (n=56)	12 (21.4)	26 (46.4)	18 (32.1)	
55-64 (n=36)	3 (8.3)	11 (30.6)	22 (61.1)	
≥65 (n=35)	3 (8.6)	2 (5.7)	30 (86.7)	<0.001
Gender				
Male (n=198)	26 (13.1)	90 (45.5)	82 (41.4)	
Female (n=163)	35 (21.5)	87 (53.4)	41 (25.2)	0.003
Marital status				
Single (n=98)	16 (16.3)	61 (62.2)	21 (21.4)	
Married (n=241)	39 (16.2)	107 (44.4)	95 (39.4)	
Divorced (n=15)	5 (33.3)	6 (40.0)	4 (26.7)	
Widowed (n=7)	1 (14.2)	3 (42.9)	3 (42.9)	0.026
Having children (n=263)				
No (n=44)	8 (18.2)	25 (56.8)	11 (25.0)	
Yes (n=219)	37 (16.9)	91 (41.6)	91 (41.6)	0.102
Natinality				
Saudi (n=352)	61 (17.3)	172 (48.9)	119 (33.8)	
Non-Saudi (n=9)	0 (0.0)	5 (55.6)	4 (44.4)	0.381
Highest level of education				
No formal education (n=13)	0 (0.0)	3 (23.1)	10 (76.9)	
Primary–intermediate school (n=12)	5 (41.7)	3 (25.0)	4 (33.3)	
Secondary school (n=89)	15 (16.9)	43 (48.3)	31 (34.8)	
Bachelor's degree (n=178)	31 (17.4)	99 (55.6)	48 (27.0)	
Postgraduate degree (n=69)	10 (14.5)	29 (42.0)	30 (43.5)	0.003
Employment status				
Unemployed (n=83)	18 (21.7)	43 (51.8)	22 (26.5)	
Employed full-time (n=187)	37 (19.8)	94 (50.3)	56 (29.9)	
Employed part-time (n==11)	1 (9.0)	5 (45.5)	5 (45.5)	
Student (n=35)	3 (9.6)	25 (71.4)	7 (20.0)	
Retired (n=45)	2 (4.4)	10 (22.2)	33 (73.4)	<0.001
Working in healthcare				
No (n=266)	45 (16.9)	130 (48.9)	91 (34.2)	
Yes (n=95)	16 (16.8)	47 (49.5)	32 (33.7)	0.994
Monthly income (Saudi Riyals)				

Less than 5,000 (n=96)	19 (19.8)	57 (59.4)	20 (20.8)	<0.001
5,000 - 10,000 (n=61)	14 (23.0)	27 (44.3)	20 (32.8)	
10,001 - 15,000 (n=60)	14 (23.3)	34 (56.7)	12 (20.0)	
15,001 - 20,000 (n=61)	11 (18.0)	28 (45.9)	22 (36.1)	
More than 20,000 (n=83)	3 (3.6)	31 (37.3)	49 (59.0)	
Duration of living in Riyadh city (Years)				
Less than 1 (n=24)				0.229
1-3 (n=13)	6 (25.0)	15 (62.5)	3 (12.5)	
4-6 (n=15)	3 (23.1)	6 (46.2)	4 (30.8)	
7-10 (n=22)	0 (0.0)	8 (53.3)	7 (46.7)	
More than 10 (n=287)	2 (9.1)	10 (45.5)	10 (45.5)	
	50 (17.4)	138 (48.1)	99 (34.5)	
Body mass index				
Underweight (n=8)	1 (12.5)	5 (62.5)	2 (25.0)	0.011
Normal (n=93)	12 (12.9)	59 (63.4)	22 (23.7)	
Overweight (n=128)	30 (23.4)	49 (38.3)	49 (38.3)	
Obese (n=132)	18 (13.6)	64 (48.5)	50 (37.9)	
Practicing regular exercise				
No (n=221)	45 (20.4)	119 (53.8)	57 (25.8)	<0.001
Yes (n=140)	16 (11.4)	58 (41.4)	66 (47.1)	
History of chrnic health problems				
No (n=259)	50 (19.3)	149 (57.5)	60 (23.2)	<0.001
Yes (n=102)	11 (10.8)	28 (27.5)	63 (61.8)	
Smoking history				
No (n=262)	45 (17.2)	135 (51.5)	82 (31.3)	0.229
Yes (n=73)	10 (13.7)	34 (46.6)	29 (39.7)	
Ex-smoker (n=26)	6 (23.1)	8 (30.8)	12 (46.1)	
Being informed about the importance of the flu vaccine				
No (n=66)	26 (39.4)	38 (57.6)	2 (3.0)	<0.001
Yes (n=295)	35 (11.9)	139 (47.1)	121 (41.0)	

Note: *Pearson`s Chi-square test

The commonly reported motivator to uptake the seasonal influenza vaccine was to prevent illness and reduce influenza complications (78.7%), followed by

protection during Umrah and Hajj (37.1%), social responsibility and collective immunity (33.5%) and positive past experience with the vaccine (27.7%).

Figure 4: Motivators to Uptake the Seasonal Influenza Vaccine

As regards the barriers of not to uptake the vaccine, the most commonly observed one was fear of side effects (75.9%), followed by misinformation or myths (41%),

prior negative experience with the vaccine (29.4%), perceived natural immunity (27.1%) and lack of knowledge or awareness (25.2%).

Figure 5: Barriersto not Uptake the Seasonal Influenza Vaccine

Discussion

There is no specific recommendation issued by the World Health Organizaion (WHO) for uptake of seasonal influenza vaccine for the general adult population aged 18–64 years [14]. In addition, very limited number of studies has been done to explore the attitude of general adult population towards seasonal influenza vaccination [15,16]. On the other hand, there is a good documentation of the importance of equity in seasonal influenza vaccination programs [17-19]. Thus, understanding the attitude of general adult population in our region towards seasonal influenza vaccine and defining their motivators and barriers of uptake the vaccine could help in overcoming challenges faced in efforts to promote vaccination.

Findings of the present study revealed that the healthcare sector was the main source of information about the importance of seasonal influenza vaccine; in the form of Ministry of Health compaigns and healthcare providers. Previous Saudi study carried out in Taif reported media and family as the primary sources of information about seasonal influenza vaccine [20]. This might reflect a promising change over the last few years

Some encouraging findings concerning the attitude of the participants towards seasonal influenza vaccine were observed in the current study such as finding that most of the participants believed that it is very easy to access flu vaccination services, mostly or completely trusted the information provided by healthcare

providers about the flu vaccine, and likely to recommend the flu vaccine to others. Additionally, almost half of them agreed that it is important for people to get the flu vaccine. Overall, almost half of general adult population expressed neutral attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccination while only 34.1% expressed positive attitude while 16.9% had negative attitude towards the vaccine. Having positive attitude was proved as an important predictor for uptaking the vaccine as seen in a study conducted online among Saudi general adult population by Sales et al (2021) who reported that participants who believed that the influenza vaccine is safe, efficacious, should be given during a specific time in the year, and were aware of their need to get seasonal influenza vaccine were more likely to receive the vaccine [12].

The current study revealed that positive attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccination was more likely to be reported among elderly people, males, married and lower educated, retired, those with higher monthly income, overweight and obese participants, those who reported practicing regular exercise, with chronic health problems and those who being informed about the importance of the flu vaccine. Some other studies also reported a relation between people’s older age and their positive attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccine [11,21]. Sales et al in their study conducted in Saudi Arabia observed that over 90% of patients with chronic diseases reported irregular uptake of seasonal influenza vaccine [12].

High risk people including elderly persons and those with history of chronic illness need more attention from healthcare providers to encourage them to uptake the seasonal influenza vaccine as in a Saudi study conducted 2017, approximately only 44% of them have uptaken the vaccine [20].

Finding more positive attitude towards the seasonal influenza vaccine among males than females could be attributed to women's concerns regarding safety of the vaccine during pregnancy [22,23].

Similar to our findings, lower education has been reported as a potential motivator toward vaccination in the United States [24], Lebanon [25], Bangladesh [26], and China [27].

The commonly reported motivators to uptake the seasonal influenza vaccine according to findings of the current study were prevention of illness and reduction of influenza complications, protection during Umrah and Hajj, social responsibility and collective immunity and positive past experience with the vaccine. Welch et al (2023) reported that the most agreed encouraging factor for influenza vaccination uptake was trust in healthcare services [9]. In United States (2019), Quinn et al observed that lower influenza vaccine uptake was associated with greater vaccine hesitancy while greater confidence and trust were associated with higher uptake of the vaccine [28].

The most frequently reported barriers of not to uptake the vaccine in the present study were fear of side effects, misinformation or myths, prior negative experience with the vaccine, perceived natural immunity and lack of knowledge or awareness. In another similar Saudi Study conducted also in Riyadh, the most frequently reported reasons for not accepting the vaccine were believe that it haven't positive benefit, no need, and believing that it might cause serious side effects [29]. Welch et al (2023) reported that negative attitude towards healthcare was the most agreed upon barrier to vaccine uptake while the most agreed encouraging factor for influenza vaccination uptake was trust in healthcare services [9]. In a systematic review carried out by Schmid et al (2017), the main reported barriers for seasonal influenza vaccine uptake were lack of confidence, inconvenience and complacency [15]. In United Kingdom (2021), Nicholls et al reported that higher calculation of disease and vaccination risk, and preference for natural immunity predicted refusal the influenza vaccine [30]. In United States (2021), Lytle et al reported that the main reasons for not uptaking the seasonal influenza vaccine were perceived ineffectiveness, perceived risk of influenza vaccination, absence of medical insurance and being non-White or Hispanic [31]. In a recent systematic review conducted by Kumar et al (2022), causes of vaccine uptake negative attitude included lack of trust in efficacy, concerns over safety, lack of need for vaccination and cultural concerns

[32]. Vaccine unawareness, confidence in the natural immunity, and concerns about safety in pregnancy were reported by others in Saudi Arabia as common barriers to uptake the vaccine [11,22,23].

Study Limitations

Some limitations of the present study should be addressed. First, its conduction online increases the possibility of selection bias as the inclusion of elderly and lower socioeconomic status subjects may be limited due to lack of internet access. Second, due to use of self-reported tool in data collection, the possibility of recall bias may be high. Third, the study was conducted in Riyadh, so the generalizability of findings over the entire Saudi population should be treated with caution. Fourth, we focused on attitude, motivators and barriers of the vaccine uptake only with ignorance of the rate of vaccine uptake. Despite of those limitations, the study carried a public health importance in tackling this subject and focusing on motivators and barriers of the vaccine uptake.

Conclusions

Majority of adult population in Riyadh expressed either neutral or positive attitude towards seasonal influenza vaccine. Elderly people (≥ 65 years), males, married participants, those with no formal education, retired participants, those with high monthly income, overweight/obese, those who reported practicing regular exercise, with chronic health problems and those who being informed about the importance of the flu vaccine were more likely than their counterparts to express positive attitude towards the vaccine. The commonly reported motivators to uptake the seasonal influenza vaccine were prevention of illness and reduction of influenza complications, protection during Umrah and Hajj, social responsibility and collective immunity and positive past experience with the vaccine while the most frequently reported barriers were fear of side effects, misinformation or myths, prior negative experience with the vaccine, perceived natural immunity and lack of knowledge or awareness. According to these findings, we recommended giving more attention to high risk group of people and encourage them to uptake the vaccine. Healthcare providers, social media platforms and mass media tools could play an important part in this issue. Mass vaccination should be organized and make it mandatory at workplaces and social gathering places as this is very important to achieve a homogeneous population-immunity level. Further, nationwide multicenteric study with sufficient sample size is highly recommended to deeply investigate this important topic in our country.

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